

Evolutionary history of *Xylella fastidiosa* based on comparative genomics.

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Once thought to be restricted to the Americas, the plant-associated bacterium *Xylella fastidiosa* has been blooming since 2013 in Europe and Asia. This bacterium infects a large host range and is responsible for plant diseases with great socio-economic consequences. Genetically diverse, this species is divided into subspecies but genetic traits governing this classification are poorly understood. We used comparative genomics of a set of nearly 50 genome sequences to gain a better knowledge on genetic traits associated to lineages and gene fluxes among lineages. We developed a software, Sklf (Specific k-mers Identification), to mine genome sequences and identify signatures of groups of interest. Genome sequences were also used to gain knowledge in the evolutionary history of the subspecies multiplex. Altogether, we provide important resources and knowledge to optimize the strategies attempted to limit the pathogen dissemination in novel areas.

Reference

Denancé N, M Briand, R Gaborieau, S Gaillard, M-A Jacques 2019. Identification of genetic relationships and subspecies signatures in *Xylella fastidiosa*. BMC Genomics 20 :239.